

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GENERAL PIANO TEACHING IN MUSIC EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the psychological characteristics of general piano teaching in music educational institutions. In the process of piano lessons, students may face psychological conditions such as difficulties, stress and self-doubt. In order to overcome such situations, the article considers the importance of an individual approach, increasing motivation and creating a positive psychological environment in the educational process. Also, the factors and psychological approaches affecting the psychological development of the student's personality in the process of piano teaching are analyzed. The article emphasizes the importance of a psychologically correct approach to the effectiveness of general piano science in the educational process.

Key words: general piano, music education, psychological characteristics, motivation, personality development, creative thinking, psychological environment, educational methods.

Introduction:

Teaching general piano science in music educational institutions has a significant impact not only on the development of students' performance skills, but also on their psychological development. Students' emotional states, motivations, self-confidence and creative thinking in the process of playing musical works depend on the teaching of piano science. Therefore, it is important for the teacher not only to teach technical skills in the course of the lesson, but also to take into account the psychological characteristics of the student's personality.

Teaching general piano science requires a psychological approach, because the process of learning and playing piano works can cause different emotions in students. During this process, some students may experience difficulties, self-doubt or stress. Therefore, it is necessary to use an individual approach in classes, to correctly assess the psychological state of students, and to use pedagogical methods aimed at increasing their creative thinking and motivation. This article analyzes the psychological characteristics of general piano teaching, the factors influencing the personal development of students, and effective teaching methods.

Material:

It is important to study the psychology of students and approach it accordingly in teaching general piano science. Materials used in the educational process should be selected in accordance with the ability, level of preparation and psychological state of the student. At the initial stage, students are taught to play simpler musical pieces, which helps to build their self-confidence and increase their interest in music. Also, in order to stimulate students creatively, the selected works should allow them to reflect and express their emotional state.

When choosing material, not only technical complexity is taken into account, but also the content and emotional expression of the works. In the course of the lesson, etudes and works are selected that encourage students to independent learning and creative thinking, and help to express freedom and emotions in performance. Educators can use music therapy methods in lessons, use pedagogical approaches aimed at maintaining students' emotional balance and increasing self-confidence.

At the same time, technical exercises, etudes, as well as texts on the historical and theoretical analysis of musical works are included among the materials used in the teaching of general piano science. These materials serve to develop students' not only performance skills, but also musical thinking, emotional and aesthetic abilities.

Discussion:

Understanding the psychological state of students and appropriate approach to them in teaching general piano science requires great experience and pedagogical skill from the teacher. Students' emotional state, motivation, ability to think creatively, and self-confidence in piano lessons are one of the important factors determining the effectiveness of lessons. The main difficulties faced by students in the process of piano performance are usually related to technical difficulties, lack of self-confidence in the correct and expressive performance of works, and underdevelopment of creative thinking.

In order to increase students' motivation during classes, pedagogues should use different methods. For example, it is important to choose a repertoire suitable for each student through an individual approach to their personal abilities and interests, to feel the content of musical works and encourage them to express it in performance. Teachers can develop their creative thinking and feelings by in-depth analysis of musical works in lessons, explaining their content, emotional aspects and aesthetic aspects to students.

In addition, the use of elements of music therapy in classes helps to improve the psychological condition of students. The calming effect of music, the selection of pieces that inspire and bring positive mood to students during piano performance have a positive effect on the educational process. At the same time, it is important to encourage students to develop their creative abilities, and to increase students' self-confidence by praising and encouraging their performance.

Discussions show that the teachers' knowledge of student psychology and the organization of lessons based on this knowledge play a decisive role in students' successful mastery of general piano science. One of the main goals of the pedagogical process is to accept each student as an individual, understand their mental state, create a positive atmosphere in the course of the lesson, and help students to discover their potential.

Result:

It is important to take into account the psychological characteristics of students in the process of teaching general piano. Piano lessons can be tailored to each student's individual abilities, emotional state, and level of motivation to develop their creative thinking, self-confidence, and musical expressiveness.

The effectiveness of the educational process is increased by the fact that teachers understand the psychological state of students and support them, use elements of music therapy in lessons and use interactive pedagogical methods. Also, directing students to independent thinking, feeling the content of musical works and expressing themselves through performance will increase their creative potential.

As a result, understanding the importance of a psychological approach in teaching general piano science, improving the pedagogical skills of teachers and creating a positive psychological environment in classes play an important role in the successful mastery of musical education by students. Therefore, in the future, continuous improvement of piano teaching process, expansion of pedagogical and psychological knowledge is one of the urgent tasks.

Summary:

Taking into account the psychological characteristics of students during the teaching of general piano science in music educational institutions ensures the effectiveness of the educational process. An individual approach to each student during the lessons, using methods suitable for their mental state, motivation and creative abilities will form students as self-confident musicians with creative thinking. The process of creating a positive psychological environment in

teaching piano, helping students to overcome difficulties and encouraging them is crucial in increasing their potential for musical expressiveness.

The analyzes carried out in the article show that increasing motivation in piano lessons, encouraging students to think creatively and focusing on their personal development increases the effectiveness of the pedagogical process. It is also important to use elements of music therapy and to choose a repertoire that develops creative expression to improve the mental state of students. Therefore, a psychologically correct approach to teaching general piano and cooperation with students is one of the main tasks of pedagogues.

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